

The Antimicrobial Activity of the Essential Oil of *Salvia officinalis* Harvested in Boumerdes

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Abstract : The Algeria by its location, offers a rich and diverse vegetation. A large number of aromatic and medicinal plants grow spontaneously. The interest in these plants has continued to grow in recent years. Their particular properties due to the essential oil fraction can be utilized to treat microbial infections. To this end, and in the context of the valuation of the Algerian flora, we became interested in the species of the family Lamiaceae which is one of the most used as a global source of spices and extracts strong families antimicrobial potency. The plant on which we have based our choice is a species of sage "*Salvia officinalis*" from the Isser localized region within the province of Boumerdes. This work focuses on the study of the antimicrobial activity of essential oil extracted from the leaves of *salvia officinalis*. The extraction is carried out by HE hydrodistillation and reveals a yield of 1.06%. The study of the antimicrobial activity of the essential oil by the method of at aromatogramme shown that Gram positive bacteria are most susceptible (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*) with a strong inhibition of growth. The yeast *Candida albicans* fungus *Aspergillus niger* and have shown moderately sensitive.

Keywords : *Salvia officinalis*, steam distillation, essential oil, aromatogram, anti-microbial activity

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